

Discourse markers: Essential elements of a successful thesis defense presentation

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Discourse markers, essential in discourse analysis, are words or phrases that link and structure content. Their correct use significantly impacts the effectiveness of presentations, especially in critical contexts like thesis defenses. This qualitative study aimed to determine how frequently discourse markers are used in thesis defense presentations. Data were collected by recording the thesis defense presentations of six students. The data were transcribed, and the analysis revealed that students employed various types of discourse markers, including micro, macro, and operator markers. Micro markers were the most commonly used, followed by macro markers and operators. Specifically, 413 micro, 200 macro, and 41 operator markers were identified. The results indicate that both micro and macro markers are essential for a successful thesis defense presentation. These results also accentuate the importance of raising students' awareness of the appropriate use of DMs in academic settings and suggest a need for further training in this area.

Keywords: Discourse Markers; Macro Marker; Micro Marker; Operator; Thesis Defense

1. Introduction

A thesis defense presentation—also called *viva voce*—is a key oral communication practice (i.e., an oral examination, typically for an academic qualification) considered a specific communicative event (cf. Samad et al., 2022). Students are required to present their research in English, before examiners and an audience, which can reflect their proficiency in oral communication. Effective use of 'discourse markers' in such presentations aids in improving oral communication by linking sentence segments and ensuring coherence and cohesion (Blakemore, 2006). Properly utilized 'discourse markers' (cf. Leonard, 2024) enhance clarity and structure, helping students

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convey their messages more effectively (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2007a, 2007b, 2012, 2023b).

Despite their importance, many students struggle with discourse markers, often relying on printed materials during presentations, which hampers their ability to speak spontaneously (Alsaawi, 2022; Patriana et al., 2016). Discourse markers, essential for managing and organizing discourse (Mahmud & Hameed, 2024), are often underappreciated in academic contexts. Awareness of discourse markers is crucial for effective information coherence and retention (Bellés Fortuño, 2006; Fung, 2003).

Research has shown that discourse markers play a significant role in educational settings, contributing to effective conversational interactions (Fung & Carter, 2007; Othman, 2010). Castro and Marcela (2009) highlighted that discourse markers help establish coherence and manage the structure of discourse. Previous studies, such as Castro and Marcela's (2009) investigation of EFL classrooms, and Saputri's (2019) research on oral presentations at Semarang State University, have demonstrated the positive impact of discourse markers on fluency and presentation quality. Castro and Marcela observed that teachers used discourse markers more frequently than students, who used them for interpersonal and literary purposes. Saputri found that micro markers were most commonly used by students, contributing to their presentation fluency.

Given these findings, further research is needed to explore the use of discourse markers in academic settings, especially in thesis defense presentations, which differ in formality from other oral contexts. This study aims to identify the most frequent types of discourse markers used in thesis defense presentations at the Graduate Study Program of English Education at Universitas Syiah Kuala, Banda Aceh, Indonesia, providing insights into their role in structuring and enhancing academic discourse.

2. Background

Many researchers have examined 'discourse markers', though no universally accepted definition exists—perhaps except for Salmani Nodoushan's (2016a, 2016b, 2019, 2021a) definitions that see them as 'supportive discourse moves' used to scaffold 'head acts' in different communicative events. Various scholars, such as Bellés Fortuño (2006), use different labels for discourse markers, including discourse-signaling devices (Polanyi & Scha, 1983), cue phrases (Knott & Dale, 1994), and pragmatic markers (Schiffrin, 1987). This study uses the term 'discourse markers' (DMs) because it is the most commonly used label in the field and aligns with the research objectives.

According to Schiffrin (2001), discourse markers are words that function as conjunctions, interjections, adverbs, and lexicalized phrases. Examples include conjunctions (e.g., and, but), interjections (e.g., oh), adverbs (e.g., now, then), and lexicalized phrases (e.g., y'know, I mean). Redeker (1991) defined discourse markers as words or phrases that highlight the relationship between utterances and the discourse context, establishing a link between speaker and listener.

Discourse markers are crucial for organizing and structuring discourse, enhancing coherence and continuity, and facilitating listener comprehension. Brinton (1996) noted that discourse markers serve various pragmatic functions at both textual and interpersonal levels. Their absence can make communication appear disjointed, even if grammar and vocabulary are correct, making it difficult for listeners to follow and understand the speaker's intended meaning. Therefore, discourse markers are linguistic expressions that connect ideas and provide meaning in communication. Despite variations in definitions, their role remains consistent in guiding listeners or readers through conversations or texts, ensuring coherence and conveying the speaker's intended meaning.

As for the characteristics of discourse markers, previous researchers have identified several features. Svartvik (1980), Schiffrin (1987), and Müller (2005) described common features of DMs as follows:

1. DMs are primarily found in spoken language: Studies show that DMs are more frequently used in oral conversations than in written texts. Müller (2005) found DMs prevalent in spoken discourse, while Biber et al. (2004) noted that specific DMs, such as 'okay' and 'so', are common in academic lectures. Fraser (1999) observed that some DMs are more frequent in written texts (e.g., 'despite'), while others are prevalent in spoken language (e.g., 'okay'). He also suggested that DMs in written texts can affect how 'spoken' they sound.
2. DMs are frequently used in spoken discourse: Research indicates that DMs are more common in spoken language than in written language (Jucker & Smith, 1998). Non-native speakers often use DMs less frequently and with less variety compared to native speakers (Fuller, 2003).
3. DMs are brief expressions: DMs are typically short phrases or single words. Othman (2010) noted that DMs can consist of one-word, two-word, or three-word units. They are used to signal the structure of a conversation or text and convey the speaker's intended meaning and goals.
4. DMs are phonologically reduced: Schiffrin (1987) described DMs as having prosodic features such as tonic stress and phonological

- reduction. Brinton (1996) also noted phonological reduction, evident in forms like 'cause' for 'because' and 'y'know' for 'you know.'
5. DMs are outside of, or weakly related to, the syntactic framework: DMs very often exhibit syntactic independence and grammatical optionality (Aijmer, 2002)—are 'disjuncts' (Salmani Nodoushan, 2018a, 2023b). They do not affect the 'truth conditions' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2006, 2018b, 2022) of an utterance and allow for various interpretations. Schiffrin (1987) explained that DMs select and display relations between discourse segments without altering grammatical structure.
 6. DMs are usually utterance-initial: Although most DMs appear at the beginning of utterances, some can occur in medial (e.g., 'however') or final positions (e.g., 'nevertheless') (Fraser, 1999). DMs create relationships between discourse segments, contributing to the flow and coherence of discourse (Fraser, 1999).
 7. DMs are difficult to categorize into typical word classes: Scholars such as Svartvik (1980), Schiffrin (1987), Fraser (1999), and Aijmer (2002) have noted the difficulty in classifying DMs into a single word class due to their varied functions and contextual usage.
 8. DMs have core meanings: Fraser (1999) adopted a grammatical-pragmatic approach, viewing DMs as phrases with core meanings that are modified by context. DMs help create coherence within a text and convey relationships between statements, facilitating a smooth discourse flow.
 9. DMs perform multiple functions: The existing literature shows that DMs typically fulfil multiple functions or sub-functions (Brinton, 1996). Aijmer (2002) supported this view, noting that DMs have various pragmatic values compared to ordinary words.

In summary, the nine common features of discourse markers (DMs) highlight their significant role in structuring and enhancing communication. DMs are predominantly used in spoken language, often appearing as brief, phonologically reduced expressions that help organize discourse and establish coherence. They are typically found at the beginning of utterances but can also occur in medial or final positions, contributing to the flow of conversation. DMs exhibit syntactic independence and can be challenging to categorize into specific word classes due to their multifaceted functions. Their core meanings, which can be modified by context, underline their importance in maintaining continuity and clarity in discourse. Overall, understanding these features provides valuable insights into how DMs facilitate effective communication and contribute to the organization and coherence of both spoken and written texts.

Deborah Schiffrin is considered one of the pioneering scholars in the study of discourse markers, which are words or phrases signaling the structure and organization of spoken or written language. According to Schiffrin (1987), discourse markers convey both semantic and pragmatic meanings. Semantic meaning refers to the literal or dictionary definition of the marker, while pragmatic meaning pertains to the contextual use of the marker and its relationship with the speaker or writer—i.e., their ‘illocutionary force’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016b, 2018b, 2019, 2021a).

Schiffrin’s (1987) view posits that discourse markers encompass both semantic and pragmatic aspects. Pragmatic meaning involves the speaker’s intended meaning, assumptions, goals, and actions, while semantic meaning relates to the marker’s grammatical structure and the relationships between words in context. Schiffrin identified 11 common discourse markers: ‘and’, ‘because’, ‘but’, ‘I mean’, ‘now’, ‘oh’, ‘or’, ‘so’, ‘then’, ‘well’, and ‘y’know’; she noted that, except for ‘oh!’ and ‘well’, all of the other DMs have meaningful uses in everyday conversational language. Accordingly, Schiffrin’s research has significantly contributed to discourse studies by providing insights into the uses and functions of discourse markers in natural language, thus informing further research in the field.

In contrast, Fraser (2009) examined discourse markers from a different angle, identifying not only semantic and pragmatic meanings but also syntactic meanings derived from language rules. Fraser (2009) categorized discourse markers into five groups:

1. Coordinate conjunctions: and, but, or, so, yet
2. Subordinate conjunctions: after, although, as, as far as, as if, as long as, assuming that, if, immediately, . . .
3. Adverbials: anyway, then, still, furthermore, however, consequently, besides, . . .
4. Prepositional phrases: above all, after all, as a consequence, as a conclusion, in fact, in general, in contrast (to that), . . .
5. Prepositions: despite, in spite of, instead of, rather, than, . . .

Fraser (2009) also identified four basic semantic relationships for discourse markers:

1. Contrastive Markers (CDMs): alternatively, although, contrariwise, contrary to expectations, conversely, despite (this/that), even so, however, in spite of (this/that), in comparison (with this/that), in contrast (to this/that), instead of (this/that), nevertheless, nonetheless, notwithstanding, on the other hand, on the contrary,

- rather (than this/that), regardless (of this/that), still, though, whereas, yet, . . .
2. Elaborative Markers (EDMs): and, above all, also, alternatively, analogously, besides, by the same token, correspondingly, equally, for example, for instance, furthermore, in addition, in other words, in particular, likewise, more accurately, more importantly, more precisely, more to the point, moreover, on that basis, on top of it all, or, otherwise, rather similarly, that is (to say), . . .
 3. Implicative Markers (IDMs): so, after all, all things considered, as a conclusion, as a consequence (of this/that), because (of this/that), consequently, for this/that reason, hence, it follows that, accordingly, in this/that/any case, on this/that condition, on these/those grounds, then, therefore, thus, . . .
 4. Temporal Markers (TDMs): then, after, as soon as, before, eventually, first, immediately afterward, meanwhile, originally, second, subsequently, when, . . .

Bellés Fortuño (2006) introduced a more sophisticated taxonomy of discourse markers, distinguishing between micro-markers and macro-markers. Micro-markers—including additional, temporal, causal, contrastive, and consecutive markers—serve to fill pauses and connect words within lectures, enhancing bottom-up processing by giving listeners additional time to process information. They also contribute to ideational significance. Micro-markers play a crucial role in providing ideational meaning within a segment of a discourse in relation to other sections (Bellés Fortuño, 2006). They serve as minor transitions that indicate links between sentences, allowing for more coherent and connected discourse. Additionally, the presence of micro-markers allows listeners to process individual segments of the discourse more efficiently because they provide more opportunities for bottom-up processing (Bellés Fortuño, 2006). As a result, listeners can better understand the flow and organization of discourse and can more easily identify key ideas and arguments being presented.

Conversely, macro-markers—including starters, rephrasers, organizers, topic shifters, and conclusion markers—indicate the macrostructure of a lecture, highlighting key points and their order, and activating listeners' pre-existing knowledge structures or 'schemata' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2010) to aid comprehension. When used in a lecture setting, macro-markers are considered more crucial than micro-markers (Chaudron & Richards, 1986). This is because they play a vital role in organizing and structuring the information presented logically and coherently. Macro-markers signal the relationship between the different parts of the lecture and help to create a clear and cohesive narrative for the audience. They help indicate the main points and structure of the

lecture, guide the listener through the information, and highlight the most important aspects (Bellés Fortuño, 2006) of the lecture.

Finally, operators include (1) markers of speaker-speech relation (i.e., attitudinal markers and pause fillers), and (2) markers of speaker-hearer relations (i.e., elicitation markers, acceptance markers, and confirmation checks). Operators as discourse markers also signal the speaker's intents and impact the 'illocutionary force' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2006, 2016a, 2022, 2024), primarily in conversational rather than written discourse. In other words, in discourse analysis, operator markers are words or phrases that signal relationships between different parts of a text or conversation (Bellés Fortuño, 2006). They are used to indicate the speaker's attitude toward the information being presented, or to signal the speaker's role in the discourse. These operator markers are important to analyze when trying to understand the meaning of a text or conversation because they reveal the speaker's attitude toward, and perspective on, the information being presented, which can be used to infer the speaker's intentions and beliefs. This is on a par with what Hyland (1994, 1996, 1998, 1999, 2000, 2001, 2004, 2005), Hyland and Milton (1997), and Hyland and Tse (2004) have called 'metadiscursive markers'. Needless to say, Bellés Fortuño's (2006) taxonomy of discourse markers has advanced our understanding of discourse markers in spoken language.

One form of spoken language is the 'thesis defense presentation' (or *viva voce*); it is the final oral assessment conducted at the end of university studies, where students present their research findings and defend their expertise before a panel of examiners (Samad & Adnan, 2018). Upon completing their thesis, the graduate student must present their research to a panel of esteemed professors and experts in their field (Fleming & Kowalsky, 2021) and defend it. This formal event, known as a 'thesis defense', serves as the final evaluation of the student's scholarly work and allows the committee to assess the student's comprehensive understanding and mastery of their research topic (Samad et al., 2024).

Terminology for the final oral test or examination varies globally. In the United States, it is referred to as an 'institutionalized pedagogical activity' (Hasan, 1994). Most European universities use the term 'public defense', while in the United Kingdom, it is commonly known as '*viva voce*' (Samad et al., 2019). During the defense, the student will provide an overview of their research project, including the background, research question, and study objectives. They will explain the methods and techniques used in their research, including data collection and analysis methods (Berndtsson et al., 2008). Additionally, the student will present their findings, including any statistical analyses or data visualizations, and discuss the implications of their research for their field

(Brubaker & Thomas, 2000). The student will also defend the validity and reliability of their research before the committee (Fleming & Kowalsky, 2021).

The defense provides an opportunity for the committee to question the student's research and ensure their thorough understanding of the topic. The committee will evaluate the quality of the research, methodology, and the overall contribution of the thesis to the field. Based on their evaluation, the committee will decide whether the thesis meets the academic standards required for awarding the degree.

It is important to note that the format and requirements for a thesis defense can vary depending on the institution and field of study (Golding et al., 2014). Students should familiarize themselves with the specific guidelines and expectations of their departments or programs prior to the defense. In essence, the oral thesis defense is a review of a completed piece of work (Samad & Adnan, 2018).

3. Method

This research focuses on spoken discourse analysis using a qualitative approach. Sugiyono (2006) stated that qualitative methods are not used to test hypotheses or theories but to describe facts through sentences with symbolism derived from informants and observed behavior. According to Creswell (2009), qualitative methods investigate unusual events by reviewing documents, observing behaviors, and conducting interviews. In this study, qualitative data were collected through audio-recording students' thesis defense presentations and transcribing the recordings into written form.

3.1. Participants

To collect the data, six students enrolled in the Graduate Study Program of English Education at Universitas Syiah Kuala, Banda Aceh, Indonesia, were selected as the participants. In doing so, a simple random sampling technique was applied, and six students were randomly chosen.

Before their thesis defense, these students must ensure all coursework is completed, except for the thesis course, and they must have their theses approved by two advisors and the chair of the department. At least one week prior to the defense, they submitted necessary documents, including thesis reviews, an evaluation reports from their advisors, and a list of committee members, to the head of the department. Those who performed their theses defense presentations in front of a panel of examiners on the appointed schedule were asked for consent to record their audio-only presentations, which usually takes about 10 to 20 minutes.

3.2. Materials

Wilkinson and Birmingham (2003) noted that research instruments are tools for gathering information pertinent to a research project, and no single tool is inherently superior to another (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2009, 2023a). In this study, an observation sheet was used to collect data containing micro markers, macro markers, and operators used by the participants in their thesis defense presentation. The data was gathered by audio recording of the students' presentations during the thesis defense using a smartphone voice recorder.

3.3. Procedure

Before collecting the data, it was necessary to ask participants permission to observe and/or audio-record their thesis defense presentations. It is important to do so to prevent unwanted situations in the future from occurring and to avoid losing essential data in the form of utterances spoken by the participants.

The data used in this study were analyzed based on the theory of DMs developed by Bellés Fortuño (2006). The taxonomy proposed by Bellés Fortuño provides a more extensive categorization of discourse indicators: micro, macro, and operator markers. The audio recordings were transcribed into a written form. All relevant information was selected, tagged, or flagged based on the type. The relevant data labels, necessary to the focus of the research, were then added to paragraphs. Furthermore, the data analysis procedures suggested by Miles et al. (2014) were used to analyze the data. The data analysis technique is divided into several stages: (a) data collection, (b) data reduction, (c) data display, and (d) conclusion or explanation.

4. Results

The observation results demonstrated that the participants used discourse markers in their thesis defense presentations. The types and frequencies of each discourse marker found were categorized based on the discourse marker framework proposed by Bellés Fortuño (2006). The results showed that the students had used micro, macro, and operator markers. The most frequently used markers were additional markers (188), and the least frequently used marker was elicitation (1).

4.1. Macro markers

As stated above, macro markers are used to indicate major transitions in speech or discourse. The presence of macro markers can enhance retention and recall. These higher-order markers are particularly useful for highlighting global movements and overall relationships in discourse.

Starter markers are used to begin discourses, as suggested by their name. Our research participants could not avoid using starter markers during their thesis defense presentations. Starter markers were used 74 times by the participants. These markers include 'for the first', 'I want to talk about', and 'first.'

Likewise, the primary function of conclusion markers is to end a discourse. Up to 27 occurrences of conclusion markers were discovered--including 'finally', 'that's all', and 'the last.' However, the students also used other words or phrases that might signal a conclusion or hint at concluding the discourse.

The students also used topic shifters in their thesis defense presentations to transition from one topic to another, whether related or unrelated to their previous discussion. The data show that they preferred the marker 'so' over the other two topic shifters, 'now' and 'actually.' The word 'so' can be ambiguous because it is also used as a consecutive micro-marker. A total of 70 topic shifter markers were identified in their presentations, with 'so' being the most prevalent.

Likewise, the goal of organizer markers is to structure a discourse, indicating a speaker's stance on what they want to say and attracting the audience's attention. Our data revealed that the participants had used 23 organizer markers during their thesis defense presentations. These markers usually include mental or action verbs such as 'discuss', 'do', and 'emphasize.' However, they should not be confused with words like 'begin', 'start', 'finish up', or 'end', as these verbs belong to starter and conclusion markers. The organizer markers identified in the research were 'I want to', 'let me', and 'let us.'

The function of rephrased markers, or rephrasers, is to restate or rephrase what a speaker has just said to ensure better comprehension by the listeners. These markers signal to the listener that the speaker is providing additional information or clarification on a previously discussed point and can help keep the conversation or presentation on track. The data demonstrated that the participants had used rephrased markers six times during their thesis defense presentations. They had used 'that is', but no other rephrased markers, such as 'I mean' or 'in other words'.

4.2. Micro markers

Micro markers were also identified in the thesis defense presentations at hand, and they were found to be the most frequent. The data showed that the students had used all types of micro markers during their thesis defense presentations. The markers included causal, temporal, additional, contrastive, and consecutive. The detailed data for each micro marker type are summarized here.

A causal marker is used to indicate the reason for an action or statement in the subsequent sentence. The data revealed that the students used 36 causal markers, including 'because', 'because of', and 'since', in their thesis defense presentations.

As for, additional markers, they were the most commonly used during the students' thesis defense presentations. The markers identified were 'and', 'or', and 'now.' The data showed that 188 additional markers had been used, with 'and' being the most frequent.

Likewise, there were 29 contrastive markers used during the students' thesis defense presentations. The types of contrastive markers used were 'but', 'however', and 'even though.' The participants had used these markers to contrast ideas in their presentations.

The participants had also used consecutive markers to indicate the outcome of an idea. In this context, 70 consecutive markers were identified, including the words 'so', 'then', and 'so that.' These markers were used to summarize what had just been said.

Finally, temporal markers were the second most frequently used discourse markers during the students' thesis defense presentations. The variants of temporal markers included 'then', 'before', and 'after.' The data revealed 90 instances, with 'then' being the most prevalent.

4.3. Operators

Operator markers are used to link a speaker to their speech and to connect the speaker with their listener or audience. The data revealed that the participants had also used operator markers during their thesis defense presentations. However, only attitudinal, pause filler, and elicitation markers had been used, while confirmation checks and acceptance markers had been left out. Below are the details.

Our data showed that the participants had used attitudinal markers 12 times in their thesis defense presentations. The markers 'I think' and 'as we know' were identified in the corpus. The participants had used these markers to capture their listeners' attention and to assume that the listeners shared the same prior knowledge as the speakers.

Elicitation markers often are used to immediately elicit further information related to a previous remark or speech. Based on our data, only one elicitation marker had been used by the students: 'why do I.' Apparently, it was employed to elicit more information about an idea and to capture the listeners' attention.

Finally, pause fillers are normally used to fill the gaps between words during the participants' presentations. The function of these markers is to give

students time to think or to fill the empty spaces between spoken words. The data revealed that 14 pause fillers using the word 'okay' and 10 using the word 'and' had been used during our participants' thesis defense presentations.

5. Discussion

After reviewing the findings, the researchers observed the significant role of discourse markers (DMs) in enhancing the effectiveness, coherence, and cohesion of students' thesis defense presentations. As stated before, DMs serve as essential linguistic tools that help structure speech, guide the audience's understanding, and maintain the flow of discourse. The analysis identified the use of various DMs, including macro, micro, and operator markers, by the students during their presentations. While some markers were employed effectively, others were less aligned with their intended functions, indicating areas for potential improvement in the students' use of these linguistic elements.

The data revealed that micro markers were the most frequently used type of DMs, significantly outnumbering both macro and operator markers. Specifically, 413 occurrences of micro markers were recorded, compared to 200 instances of macro markers and 41 instances of operator markers. This prevalence of micro markers suggests that students rely heavily on these markers to connect ideas, indicate relationships between concepts, and maintain the logical flow of their arguments. The micro markers served various functions, including additional, temporal, causal, contrastive, and consecutive functions, each contributing to the overall coherence of the presentation (cf. Bellés Fortuño, 2006).

In contrast, macro markers—which include starters, rephrasers, organizers, topic-shifters, and conclusion markers—were used to signal larger transitions in discourse, organize content, and emphasize key points (cf. Bellés Fortuño, 2006). The comparatively lower frequency of macro markers indicates that, while students are aware of the need to structure their presentations, there may be room for improvement in how they manage and signal major transitions and shifts in their discourse. For example, the rephraser markers, which help clarify points for better comprehension, were used infrequently, with only six instances recorded. This suggests that students may not be fully utilizing the potential of rephraser markers to ensure their audience's understanding, indicating a potential area for further training or emphasis in preparation for thesis defenses.

Operator markers were the least frequently used, with only 41 instances recorded. These markers, which include attitudinal, pause filler, and elicitation markers, are typically used in interactive communication to establish a connection between the speaker and the audience or to manage the speaker's

stance and pacing (cf. Bellés Fortuño, 2006). The rarity of operator markers in the thesis defense presentations is consistent with Bellés Fortuño's argument that these markers are more common in dialogues or interactive settings, where direct engagement with the audience is required. In a formal presentation like a thesis defense, where the focus is primarily on delivering information rather than interacting with the audience, operator markers may be perceived as less necessary or perhaps even redundant.

The results also highlighted that students employed a wide range of DMs with different functions. Rephraser markers were used infrequently, with only six instances recorded. On the other hand, the most commonly used DMs were 'and' and 'then', which served multiple functions. The word 'and' was frequently used as both an additional marker and a pause filler, helping to connect ideas and fill pauses in speech, while 'then' was used to indicate temporal sequences or logical conclusions. These findings highlight the students' reliance on certain DMs, while other potentially beneficial markers are underutilized, suggesting areas for pedagogical focus.

These findings align with those of Saputri (2019), who also identified micro markers as the most frequently used DMs in oral presentations. However, while Saputri's study focused solely on the occurrence of micro and macro markers, this research extended the analysis to include operator markers in thesis defense presentations, offering a more comprehensive view of how students manage their discourse during such formal events. It should be noted that this study explored the use of DMs in the context of thesis defense presentations, providing insights that are directly applicable academic presentations and public speaking in higher education settings.

6. Conclusion

The conclusion of this study emphasizes the critical role of discourse markers (DMs) in thesis defense oral presentations, as they facilitate effective communication and ensure the coherence and organization of arguments. The analysis reveals that a strong thesis defense presentation establishes a clear connection between the speaker, their speech, and the audience, with DMs playing a pivotal role in this process. However, the findings also highlight instances of overuse or improper use of DMs, particularly micro markers, which were the most frequently used, appearing 413 times, compared to 200 instances of macro markers and 41 instances of operator markers.

These results accentuate the importance of raising students' awareness of the appropriate use of DMs in academic settings and suggest a need for further training—or 'remedial instruction' à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021b, 2023a)—in this area. This research provides valuable insights for English learners aiming to enhance their speaking skills, particularly in oral presentations, by

offering an understanding of the various types of frequently used DMs. Additionally, English teachers, especially those focused on teaching presentation skills, can use these findings to demonstrate the proper use of DMs and address common errors in English oral presentations, ultimately helping students avoid the overuse of DMs.

Given the limitations of this study, where most students presented by reading slides, future research should consider a broader range of data sources and explore the use of DMs in various formal speaking contexts. This would provide a more comprehensive understanding of DM usage and its impact on different types of academic presentations.

Authors' Statement

All authors confirm that they collaborated in the discussion and development of this paper. The first author originated the idea and gathered the data, while the second, third, and fourth authors contributed to the overall concept, as well as the editing and refinement of the article.

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